

Proliferation of Higher and University Educational Establishments in Rural Areas of Bulungu Territory in the Republic of Democratic Agriculture of the Congo

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Abstract:- Our study analyzes the persistence of the proliferation of higher education and university institutions in the Democratic Republic of Congo in rural areas of the territory of Bulungu, Kwilu Province, Democratic Republic of Congo by politicians, teacher-politicians, teachers and some officials of these educational institutions as well as the local populations of these rural areas. While the balance sheet of the contributions of this phenomenon shows the dominance of disadvantages over advantages. Notwithstanding these enormous challenges and closures of some institutions for reasons of viability and/or reliability, this phenomenon still persists. The two major causes of this persistence are that higher education and university institutions are seen as weapons of struggle for inter-group hegemony and means of financial enrichment.

Using observation, documentary, interview with a few people constituting our work sample, we obtained the following results:

- 26% of forecasts in favour of territorial decentralisation
- 20% in favour of the development of the region
- 14.1% in favour of financial research
- 12% in favour of proximity
- 9% in favour of hegemonic motives
- 7% in favour of employment
- 5.3% in favour of indiscipline (disloyalty) and impunity
- 4% of forecasts in favor of the Presidential and Legislative elections of 2006, 2011 and 2018
- 2.6% in favour of solidarity

Keywords :- Proliferation, Higher and university education institution, Swarming, Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC).

I. INTRODUCTION

From 1954 to 1980, the Democratic Republic of Congo had only 31 institutions of higher education and university. Meanwhile, the student population was only growing, creating demographic pressure within these institutions. According to studies conducted at that time by J. Boute and Léon de Saint Moulin, for a real or estimated population of 26,377,000 people between 1979-1980, the projection of student numbers from 0.1% of the population to 26377 students; 0.2% to 52754 and 0.3% to 79131 students.¹

In order to respond to this situation, the Congolese state decided to spin off in 1982 and liberalize its higher education and university system in 1986. With liberalization, natural and legal persons were now allowed to establish higher institutes and universities. As a result of these two measures, the number of establishments increased from 31 to 70 at the end of the 1980s.

From 1990 to date, the implementation of these two strategies has resulted in a dramatic overabundance of institutions in every province of the country. In the territory of Bulungu, in the political-administrative province of Kwilu, the number of academic institutions increased from 1 (1967-1989) to 28 institutions and 14 extensions or classes relocated during the period 1990-2021. 19 establishments and 2 extensions are located in urban areas and the 9 establishments and 12 other extensions are located in rural areas.

Located in the center of the African continent, the Democratic Republic of Congo, DRC, in acronym, is facing multiple problems of various natures including the proliferation of higher education and university institutions. The proliferation of ESU institutions in the DRC arose in the context of the spin-off and liberation of ESU. Spin-off in 1982 while liberalization in 1986. The balance sheet of the contributions of this phenomenon indicates that there is dominance of disadvantages over advantages. It appears 4

¹ J.Boute and Léon de SaintMoulin : "projections of student enrolment according to demographic change considerations", p.33

essential advantages on more than 10 points of disadvantage.²

A. Contributions of the proliferation of ESU institutions

• Benefits

➤ *Abolition of regional quotas.* Before the advent of spin-offs and the liberalization of ESU, the higher and university education system suffered from regional quotas, which required the different regions (provinces) to send a proportionately small sample of applicants applying for higher or university studies to the few institutions available in the country. This principle of regional quotas deprived some provinces of the freedom to have their daughters and daughters study, even the most desirable. The advent of the spin-off and liberalization of ESU has broken this phenomenon by granting all holders state diplomas wishing to continue their training at higher and university level.

➤ *Employment. Speaking of unemployment,* President Joseph KABILA KABANGE noted in his speech of August 12, 2013 to the Congolese population, the decrease in unemployment in the DRC, Congo, from 19.41% of the active population in 2005 to 6.86% in 2011. According to our surveys conducted in December 2020, the number of jobs created in the territory of Bulungu since the advent of the spin-off and liberalization of the ESU is estimated at 3,600 people hired (academic, scientific, administrative, technical and manual staff) in ESU institutions.³

➤ *Proximity.* Extensions and relocated auditoriums have given students the opportunity to undertake their studies in their surrounding environments or to get closer to their training environments. In the past, many students moved from their usual living environments to undertake studies at very distant distances. With the advent of extensions and offshore audiences, the situation is no longer the same.

➤ *Economics of finance.* It is energy conservation in financial terms. As we know, the shift from one point to another causes expenditure. The advent of spin-offs and liberalization of ESU has minimized some travel-related costs.

• Disadvantages

- a) Unequal distribution of establishment locations :
The distribution of establishments across the different provinces indicates that North Kivu leads with 151 or 17.9% followed by Kinshasa with 77 or 9.1% of the total of 843 registered establishments and at the bottom of the scale come the provinces of Tshuapa with 4 or 0.5%; Sud-Ubangi with 5 or 0.6% and Bas-Uélé with 6 or 0.7% of establishments out of the total of 843.⁴

In the territory of Bulungu, the chosen space for our present study, this inequality in the distribution of institutions is marked on the one hand by the dominance of higher pedagogical institutes (14 out of 40 institutions, or 35%) and on the other hand by the dominance of institutions in the Kipuka sector 17 out of the 40 ESU institutions listed, i.e. 43% against: 4 (10%) in Kilunda; 1 (3%) in Dwe; 1 (3%) in Imbongo; 2 (5%) in Kkenge; 5 (13%) in Kwilu-Kimbata; 7 (18%) in Luniungu; 1 (3%) in Mikwi, 1 (3%) in Niadi-Nkara and 0 (0%) in Nko.

- b) Overload of teachers and students
From 1 to 31 December 2020, the university community of the DRC experienced several deaths, among which, 39 Professors of the University of Kinshasa (UNIKIN) were registered. In view of the history of this academic institution, it was once that the number of deaths of its professors reached these figures. The main cause of these deaths was attributed to COVID-19. However, according to the Association of Professors of the University of Kinshasa (APOKIN), there were only 06 (15%) professors who actually died from COVID-19 while 33 (85%) died as a result of difficult working conditions, failure to manage diseases.⁵

As we had unpacked in the upstream passages, most ESU institutions emerged from the proliferation of qualified teachers. The territory of Bulungu has 72 professors (permanent and visitors all combined) for a general number of 7558 students and whose ratio gives 105 students per teacher in terms of pedagogical supervision while the universal standard is set at 20 students per teacher.

² MUSUYI ATAR Barthélemy (Cfr. Our study presents)

⁴ ESU Statistical Yearbook 2015-2016, P.

⁵ Patient LIGODI : «*RDC : why this excess mortality among teachers at the University of Kinshasa?*», Radio France Internationale (RFI), Kinshasa, 03 December 2020, 04:55

To run their schools, they rely on the manpower of visiting teachers. They spend most of their time in their parent institutions and report to these institutions only after completing their hourly duties where they are permanent. It is only towards the end of the academic year that they very often rush to go to these institutions where they are invited in order to teach the subjects that are submitted under their responsibilities. It happens that some because of lack of time or discouragement related to the mediocrity of the rate of payment of hourly, transport or food charges, abandon their charges which are quickly redistributed to other visiting teachers. This situation has as a corollary, the overview of the teachings which in turn also overloads the students. The latter, overwhelmed by avalanches of teaching sessions in very short time, are subject to attend classes at an urgent pace every day, even on public holidays. Unfortunately, there are such occasions that subjects planned to be taught in two or three months are taught for only a few weeks. Faced with such a situation, the evidence of treatment of students' work can only be significant.

In addition to the problem that overburdens students, it is the support beyond the fees they pay officially, the food care of teachers in some institutions, especially in rural areas.

c) Lack of viability

The issue of the sustainability of education is a major concern at present. Indeed, the viability audit of higher education and university institutions, carried out in 2010, concludes that out of 508 organized courses, 235 or 52% have been classified as unviable and should be closed; 32% in the intermediate state requiring adjustments and only 16% have been viable. As for the 634 higher education institutions organizing other courses, the results of the survey indicate that 25% of institutions were viable; 41% in intermediate situations and 34% proved to be unsustainable.⁶

d) Failure of PSI and ISTP cooperation with Faculties of Education

Specialized in research in terms of education, the Faculty of Education Sciences has for vocation, the enrichment of the educational sector. Having also the mission of training children's trainers for the secondary and primary levels, however, the PSI and ISPT are normally called upon to cooperate with the Faculties of Educational Sciences and finally to benefit from its research fruits. Nevertheless, this cooperation is almost non-existent because each of these parties is camped in its own corner.

e) Transport difficulties

The lack of qualified teachers in higher and university education means that the majority of State institutions as well as private ones do not have their own teachers. To run their institutions, they resort to visiting teachers. In most cases, these teachers reside in urban areas *in relation* to the places where they are called upon to render their services. This requires that their movements be covered by the requesting institutions.

On the side of these host institutions, the means are proving difficult. In rural areas in particular, travel is made on foot, by canoes (motorized or non-motorized), bicycles, motorcycles, trucks, minibuses, buses and very rarely by plane despite the distances.

Aligned with the class schedules, it happens that the ticket for the travel of the visiting teachers does not arrive on time. Patriotism or charity obliging, visiting teachers sometimes take charge of themselves and pay for their travel with their own means which are reimbursed with difficulty or not.

f) Food difficulties

Institutions organize themselves here in two ways to feed their visitors. In the first case, they allocate to each of their guests a sum of money and the visitor takes care of himself for his food. Nevertheless, the problem that arises in this formula is the insufficiency of the amount that is made available to the visitor. Without any exaggeration on our part, some institutions in rural areas pay a visiting teacher 1000 Congolese Francs (DRC) as alimony fees per day.

In the second case, the host institution organizes the kitchen for its visitors itself. Here, too, the problems are acute, particularly the quantitative and qualitative inadequacies. It is not uncommon to find 5, 6, 7 or even 8 or 9 visiting teachers dipping their fingers on the same plate during a meal without taking into account hygiene. It is therefore not surprising to see teachers fall into malnutrition.

g) Difficulties related to the accommodation of teachers and internal students

In terms of accommodation, the conditions are not good either. The majority of proliferated institutions lack guests. They lodge their visitors in the houses of certain leaders of their establishments or they resort to parishes, missions or the politico-administrative authorities of the place, if not with their acquaintances. For some institutions that have these facilities, the situation is almost the same. These transient houses often do not require reliable conditions that can satisfy visitors. It is therefore not uncommon to find guests with very

⁶ Education and Training Sector Strategy 2016-2025, P.30

cramped rooms, unclean, guests who do not have the laundry room, etc.

h) Problems related to teachers' and students' leisure
Provision is made in terms of leisure for visiting teachers who come to work in the majority of institutions. No sports fields or equipment, no televisions or radios for them to get information, no internet café, the list is not exhaustive. In some places where state-of-the-art equipment (internet) is available, the problem of refueling installed machines is often mentioned.

i) Resource gaps

During the 2015-2016 academic year, higher education institutions used 21,799 computers, of which 31.3% were for administrative use and 68.7% for pedagogical use. Less significant figure in terms of the number of institutions, administrative staff and students.

a. From an infrastructural, material and financial point of view

The glaring deficiencies are noted here and there. As an illustration, here is what the table above presents to us. Out of 92 ESU institutions (public and private together) surveyed during the 2015-2016 academic year, statistics indicate that 125 or 13.55% of institutions operate in buildings that have been transferred to them, 338 or 36.65% institutions are tenants and only 459 or 49.78% of institutions in their own institutions.

At the national level, statistics tell us that 50% of ESU establishments operate in their own sites while the other 50% do not have their own infrastructure. Of the latter category, 37% are tenants and 13% operate in infrastructure transferred to them by third parties. This situation is reflected with some differences that of the territory of Bulungu in this regard; of the 39 ESU institutions, i.e. 100% of institutions that we surveyed, none of them Or 0% institutions operate in disposal infrastructures; 13 or 33.3% in rental premises and 26 or 66.6% in their own buildings.⁷

In the territory of Bulungu, of the 28 establishments and 14 extensions of ESU that we have listed, only 2 institutions or 5.1% benefit from subsidies in particular: the Catholic Higher Technical Institute of Kikwit (ex. IFACK) and the Higher Pedagogical Institute of Belemiesi.

b. From the personal point of view (qualified teachers) at ESU

The ratio of student supervision to teacher recorded during the academic year 2015-2016 at ESU within Higher Pedagogical Institutes, Higher Technical Institutes as well as within Universities and Faculty Institutes in the public sector is 13 students for 1 teacher and per type of teaching, 7 students for 1 teacher in PSI and 15 students for 1 teacher in IST and Universities. These rates seem to meet the international standard but it is not so because is a teacher assigned to ESU, than the holder of a doctoral degree.⁸

With regard to the rate of qualified teachers (holders of doctoral degrees), the ratio is 102 students to 1 professor. So, a deficient ratio. However, taken by sector and type of education, in the public sector, there is 1 teacher for every 58 students in universities, 162 in PSI and 278 in STIs.

As for the private sector, the ratio cannot be determined accurately because all private sector institutions use public sector teachers. It should also be noted that ESU has more unqualified teachers (87.5%) than qualified teachers (12.5%). In the same perspective, the data published by the Minister of Higher and University Education, Stève MBIKAYI dated Wednesday, June 06, 2018, inform that the DRC has 3,000 qualified teachers and 400,000 students. That is, an average of 200 students to be supervised by a professor. As can be seen, this student-teacher ratio does not meet UNESCO standards in this area; which require a ratio of 20 students per professor.⁹

c. From the point of view of student numbers

The overall number of ESU students in Bulungu territory is 7,558 students for the 2019-2020 academic year for a general population of 1,424,238 individuals. Compared to this population, the number of students stands out at 14,424 students. It thus appears that this figure (14,424 students) is less than 100,000 students. Indeed, the universal rule in this area says that for a population of 1,000,000 inhabitants, you must have 100,000 students. And the causes at the root of this lack of student numbers in ESU institutions in this region emanate from various origins including: exodus, poverty, the multiplication of institutions if not extensions

⁸ Ditto.

⁹ NEW 24: « *Higher Education in the DRC: the Government plans to revive bourses study abroad to scientific staff and gifted students* », June, 2018, [http:// : 24 Newagency.com/2018/06/07](http://www.newagency.com/2018/06/07)

⁷ *Statistical Yearbook of Higher and University Education: academic year 2015-2016*, Kinshasa, May 2018, p.58

and delocalized audiences, etc. the majority of the population in rural areas being poor and the rural environment itself being also less developed, Most young people leave this environment to settle in urban areas, it seems more developed, where it makes "better to live".¹⁰

- j) Unfair competition between establishments
Competition is by definition, the dispute of a clientele between traders. As for disloyalty, it is dishonesty, infidelity to established rules. In the case of the dispute, without observance of the ethical rules that is practiced by educational operators at the ESU, in particular in the creation of extensions or audiences relocated near an institution of the same nature from the point of view of the courses in the same geographical air, the neglect of the criteria for enrolling students, the bias of the criteria during the deliberations sessions in order to inflate the number of students, to round up pocketed incomes, to make the reputation of his institution. Indeed, the swelling of student numbers gives ESU institutions the appearance of large institutions, institutions of great renown as if the latter depended exclusively on the number and yet, it is not so. The minimal number of students thus pushes the managers of state as well as private institutions to multiply institutions in the direction of extensions or delocalized audiences.

- k) Confusion of duration of the daytime and evening vacation
The duration of training to obtain the title of graduate in daytime vacation is 3 academic years while it is 4 years in a vesper vacation. However, this principle is not respected as such in some institutions of ESU emanating from the Proliferation (especially in rural areas). In some circles, evening training is likely to be confused with daytime vacation. Instead of 4 years, evening training lasts 3 years on an equal footing with daytime training.

Despite all that has already been said about the challenges of the ESU of the DRC, nothing always seems to bring the Congolese education system to significant changes capable of revolutionizing its society. The same mistakes decried yesterday are repeated today. Continuing education is given on the basis of programmes that still do not harmonize with the realities on the ground. As always, as if nothing had happened, "useless brains" are produced.¹¹

- l) Further decline in the quality of training
There is a growing decline in the quality of training. What proves the mismatch between the levels of studies and the related knowledge of students are the multifaceted mediocrity manifested by a large part of students in training or graduates, such as grammar errors in their oral as well as written expressions, the inability to hold a speech in French for a long time, the decrease in rigor of the deliberative criteria, the carrying out of state examinations and TFC and dissertations by teachers instead of students, the practice of intrigues in the state exam and the phenomena "connection, monitoring and lack of coast".¹²¹³

B. Closure of higher education and academic institutions deemed unreliable and/or unsustainable

Ministerial orders: No. 111 of 29/7/2015; n°122 and n°123 of 17/10/2015 and n°174 of 19/12/2015 have all successively focused either on the closure of some establishments, or on the prohibition of operation of extensions or the prohibition of operation of some establishments and extensions throughout the Democratic Republic of Congo. Such as, the Higher School of Water Technology Sciences in the City Province of Kinshasa, the Kindu Academy, the extension of the University of Peace of the DRC / Goma located in Kinshasa, the audience relocated to Kole of the Higher Institute of Yambula, etc., the list is not exhaustive.¹⁴

In 2021, this operation to close or prohibit the operation of higher education and university institutions continued with the closure of the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Bandundu. A few months later, this faculty resumed its activities under the same conditions. These two observations, the dominance of disadvantages over the advantages of the contributions of the proliferation of institutions on the one hand and non-compliance with decisions taken, lead us to know:

- "What motivates politicians, leaders, promoters and local populations, especially in rural areas of the Democratic Republic of Congo, DRC, in acronym, to persist the proliferation of higher education and university institutions?"

As a hypothetical we say that the reasons for the persistence of the proliferation of academic institutions in the Democratic Republic of Congo are numerous, including: proximity, employment, profit-seeking, hegemony, disloyalty, the search for profit; disloyalty; the development of one's native environment, etc. However,

¹² MUSUYI ATAR Barthélemy et alii in « *State Examination in the DRC* », crossroads, Volume n°4, PP 159-178.

¹³ Alfred LUKAMBIL : « Theophilus MBEMBA at war against the phenomena connection, monitoring and lack of coast », Journal Forum des AS, Kinshasa, February 15, 2015.

¹⁴ Office of the Minister in charge of Higher and University Education of the Republic Democratic of Congo, Kinshasa, 2015.

¹⁰ NGUB'USIM MPEY NKA Richard: for the refoundation of the university in Congo;

¹¹ Emile BONGELI : "*Congolese University: manufactures useless brains*"

beyond all these motivations at the origin of the persistence of the proliferation of academic institutions in the Democratic Republic of Congo, DR Congo, in acronym is that the institutions have become weapons of the struggle in the quest for hegemony between communities (political, intellectual, confessional, intertribal, inter-sector politico-administrative or inter-provinces politico-administrative).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Among the authors who have spoken of the proliferation of secondary and university education institutions, we single out NGUB'USIM MPEY NKA Richard. In his article entitled: " The phenomenon of community universities in Congo: Innovation or additive to the crisis of higher education and education ?", Ngub'Usim believes that despite the challenge to the development of community universities, the presence of these has been an opportunity for the system of higher education and education. niversitaires, of the voluntary blockade that it experienced during almost all of the Mobutian reign. These community universities, he adds, have brought innovation at several levels, among others: in terms of the nature of the institutions, their funding system, their locations and in terms of programs and training.

- From the point of view of the nature of these institutions, as institutions designed and created by the will of local communities. Decentralized in the face of the Unaza of sad memory, these Community Universities advocate a higher education and a level of proximity.
- On the other hand, they do not appear to be strictly private or entirely public, because they belong to local (provincial) populations who identify themselves and consider them as their own heritage.
- As for the level of funding, the same author informs us that the partnership financing of these Community universities was inspired by public sector institutions which had changed their minds to rely solely on the uncertain intervention of the government in solving problems.

Turning to programmes and training, NGUB'USIM believes that student numbers and training and working conditions in Community universities are relatively more favourable to good pedagogy than in the overcrowded and equally ill-equipped faculties of the three former public universities. Ultimately, according to the author of the article "The phenomenon of Community Universities in Congo: Innovation or additive to the ESU crisis?", the Community University has alleviated the problem of overcrowding experienced by the three former universities.¹⁵

Indeed, Ngub'Usim praises the development of ESU institutions in this case, Community Universities. In fact, it

leads to proliferation the sense of simple development while we conceive it in a pejorative sense, that is, an anarchic development leading to negative or perverse emerging effects. In view of thoughts this author, we say that it is normal in relation to the context in which his study was carried out. It should be remembered that the study conducted by NGUB'USIM was carried out at the beginning of the process of development of higher and university education. It should also be noted that during this period there were no presidential and legislative elections for politicians and other operators to use them in the creation of higher education and university institutions. as means of political marketing during their electoral campaigns, there was no territorial decentralization, there were no people who considered higher education establishments and universities as means of economic production, finally, the level of moral degradation is not too mediocre as it is today.

Unlike NGUB'USIM, which finds the development of educational institutions in general and Community Universities in particular laudatory, MASHAKO MAMBA Léonard and MBEMBA FUNDU Théophile, stigmatize the proliferation of educational institutions and universities.

Surprised by the speed of increase in the number of institutions created in record time (250 establishments in May and 800 in August 2008, an increase of 550 institutions created in the space of only 3 months), without respecting the standards required in this area. MASHAKO finds that the gravediggers of the SHigher Education and University are none other than his own managers and trainers as well as the politicians.

Thus, in order to put an end to these disorders in the field of higher education and education, he considered that a reform had become imperative.¹⁶

In the same vein, Théophile MBEMBA advocates the sanitation of the S U uperieur and university education of the Democratic Republic of Congo, in view of all the vices that plague it (the connection, the lack of ribs, the commodification of practical work, the fanciful and irresponsible organization of defenses of end-of-cycle work, the disorderly organization of the third cycle, etc.¹⁷

The observations made by these two personalities are more eloquent in the sense that they were both at the head of the Ministry of Higher Education and Universitaire. Endorsing their vision, we say that they were also the actors who promoted the debacle of higher education and education insofar as they delivered approvals of the establishments of the higher education and the university to politicians and other operators, without prior and

¹⁵ NGUB'USIM MPEY NKA Richard : "The Community University Phenomenon: Innovation or additive to the ESU crisis?", Revue de Psychologie et des Sciences de l'Education, Faculté de Psychologie et des Sciences de l'Education, Volume 1, Number 1, Kinshasa, 1999, P.12

¹⁶Journal le Phare « Latest info », Kinshasa, 18 February 2009.

¹⁷Alfred LUKAMBA : « I am : Théophile MBEMBA at war against phenomena; Plugging, tracking and missing ribs », Journal Forum des AS, Kinshasa, 09 February 2015.

responsible studies. despite their knowledge of the perverse effects and the social positions on which they stood.

III. METHODOLOGY

To produce the data for this study, first read the information in various books, journals and journals in libraries and online. Secondly, we crisscrossed through the ten sectors of the territory of Bulungu, from 1 to 30 May 2022 to list all the institutions of higher education and university and at the same time, we spoke with one or the other member targeted by us as a respondent, therefore, an element of our sample. This type of sampling involves the selection of the closest and closest individuals, the most accessible individuals who are included in the study as they present themselves at a specific location, at a specific time, until the desired sample size is obtained.¹⁸

Not having a scholarship and evolving with little financial means to make several trips for the same cause, this methodology was a great help to us.

About this territory Bulungu, the latter is located at 4°33' south latitude and 18°35' east latitude¹⁹. It has a density of 94 inhabitants / km² and a population of 1,256,663 inhabitants in 2018. The territory of Bulungu occupies a geographical area of 13,404 km² of area. It consists of 10 sectors and several ethnic groups that speak the national language *Kikongo ya leta*. The population of Bulungu is very hospitable. However, very reserved to deliver certain information especially to people who are not familiar to them.

As mentioned above, to build our database, we went through all the institutions and academic extensions located in this territory. During this round, we listed 28 institutions as well as 14 extensions of higher and university education (higher institutes and universities all combined) while until the end of the 1980s it had only one academic institution; "Kikwit Higher Pedagogical Institute".

On the epistemological level, we have resorted to the "methodical individualism" method of the French sociologist Raymond Boudon. In fact, this method establishes that social actions are the result of individual facts or behaviors, even when these are subject to the influence of collective norms or values. The structured set of human relations is no longer passively shaped by the weight of conditioning, but results from clashes between divergent rationalities. Hence the consideration of the intentional and strategic dimension of the actors²⁰. The outcomes (emergent effects) of these individual behaviors or facts may be independent of the will of the positive or perverse actors.

There are perverse effects when a happy result is expected, however, unfortunately something else happens which modifies the initial conditions which give different results from what were expected. The perverse effects may be due to:

- cognitive and emotional shortcomings related to social psychology. In relation to our present study, these cognitive and emotional dimensions marry with the collective and individual representations of the actors at the basis of the persistence of this proliferation of higher education and university institutions in the Democratic Republic of Congo in general and particularly in the rural areas of the territory of Bulungu where each sector has its academic institution(s). Students and skills in one sector should not leave their environment to study and work in another. These institutions are managed by the indigenous people of the place where they are located. If the institution is headed by a person who is not linked to this political-administrative sector, it is opposed. So, as can be seen, the criterion of meritocracy is neglected in favor of mediocracy.
- elements ignored at the time of the decision, whether this ignorance is general or only limited to the decision-making circle (which ignores the clearly stated warnings of the better informed).²¹ In fact, the inadequate higher and university education system was facing demographic demand. To respond to this statistical deficiency of establishments, it has resorted to spin-offs and liberalization (democratization).

Nevertheless, the multiplication (emergent effect) of higher education and university institutions, resulting from poorly regulated spin-off and liberalization strategies, lacking clear and precise principles, has created unexpected disorders (perverse effects), mainly the overabundance of the number of academic institutions; a spatial distribution and between partners in higher and university education, etc.

This method of "methodological individualism" was accompanied by the techniques of direct and indirect observation, documentary, accidental sampling and maintenance. In relation to our assumptions, these tools have given us the following results:

- 26% of forecasts in favour of territorial decentralisation
- 20% in favour of the development of the region
- 14.1% in favour of financial research
- 12% in favour of proximity
- 9% in favour of hegemonic motives
- 7% in favour of employment
- 5.3% in favour of indiscipline (disloyalty) and impunity
- 4% of forecasts in favor of the Presidential and Legislative elections of 2006, 2011 and 2018
- 2.6% in favour of solidarity

¹⁸ André MASIALA ma SOLO and Alii : "Social Sciences and Humanities Researcher's Guide: Writing and Presenting scientific work", Centre Educatif Congolais, Kinshasa, 2012, P.66

¹⁹Wikipedia

²⁰ Gilles Ferréol et al.: "Dictionary of Sociology", Armand Colin (3rd edition), Paris, 2004, p.93

²¹fr.wikipedia.org.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the analyses provide information rather than that instead of the dominance of the struggle for intergroup hegemony, it is rather territorial decentralization that dominates as well as the development of the region. Although represented by 9% of forecasts, the struggle for hegemony comes to the fore. During interviews, some respondents simulated this hegemonic struggle under the concepts of development of their region, territorial decentralization and proximity to places of study for their children. Some languages did not hesitate to reveal to us what they meant by proximity, the development of their country as well as territorial decentralization. This is very understandable through their following statements in Kikongo ya leta: "bo luta beto na nki?", "beto ke songa bo ke kwaku mpi bantu kele", "beto lenda vanda ve kaka na nima ya bantu". All these words illustrate the primacy of hegemonic motives over others. These words in Kikongo ya leta mean in French: "In what way is it beyond us?), "we show them that there are also people here", "we cannot accept to always be behind the people".

During this research, we have set ourselves the objectives of knowledge of causes beyond those that are already known such as collective representations of higher education, territorial decentralization, the presidential and legislative elections of 2006, 2011 and 2018, the search for finances, solidarity, hegemony, etc., which are at the basis of the persistence and amplification of anarchy. in the development process of the DRC ESU.

In addition, we aimed to create the consequences of this social phenomenon and propose appropriate solutions to this problem.

We also carried out this study using the injected light of the researchers who preceded us. The convergence between our study and theirs is at the level of the field of study (the proliferation or development of higher and university education). However, the divergences quickly emerge in the sense that we discovered that higher education and university institutions in rural areas of Bulungu territory were used as weapons of hegemonic struggle.

As for the main implications, from the scientific point of view, they are the further reduction of student training, the consideration of mediocrity over meritocracy, in short, the desacralization of the Congolese education system.

On the social level, these are; libertinism, the contradiction of the vocation of harmonious development, the failure of proximity and daily monitoring of higher and university education in provinces, territories and / or sectors. In short, the failure of the education system with regard to its vocation to improve the quality of its education system. Hence we suggest the equitable spatial distribution of higher education and university institutions and the unification not of institutions and conviviality between fellow citizens living in rural areas of the territory of Bulungu.

Our present study raises new directions of studies including the search for ways of harmonious planning of educational institutions in rural areas of the territory of Bulungu.

The complementary work that these new orientations can give rise to interdisciplinary encounters.

V. CONCLUSION

Starting from the observation that the partners of the higher education and university system of the Democratic Republic of Congo persist and amplify the proliferation of higher education and university institutions despite the challenges that plague it, we wanted to know the root causes, the scientific and social consequences. And, in relation to the causes and incidences, propose solutions to stop this phenomenon altogether.

In the search for these causes, the presuppositions relating to them answering our research question are: the search for hegemony, the search for development, territorial decentralization, elections, etc.

In this study, our contribution is at the level of knowledge of the proliferation of higher education and university institutions as means or weapons of hegemonic struggle in rural areas of the territory of Bulungu. Hence our calls to fellow citizens in the corner of the Congolese national space to come together to plan.

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